

Adjusting Snakemake's maximum File Size for Checksums

Snakemake Hackathon 2025 - Report

1 Adjusting Snakemake's Maximum File Size for Checksums

1.1 Authors

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1.2 Description

This work was completed as part of the Snakemake Hackathon 2025.

1.2.1 Problem

Snakemake calculates checksums for input and output files during DAG building to determine if a rule needs to be re-executed. For very large files, computing these checksums can be a significant performance bottleneck, slowing down the DAG generation process. Previously, Snakemake had a fixed maximum file size for which checksums were computed. Files exceeding this size were considered unchanged, potentially leading to incorrect results if the file content *had* changed.

1.2.2 Solution

This work item introduces the `--max-checksum-file-size` parameter to the Snakemake CLI. This parameter allows users to adjust the maximum file size (in bytes) for which checksums are computed. By increasing this limit, users can ensure that checksums are calculated for larger files, improving the accuracy of the DAG building process. Conversely, decreasing the limit can improve performance for workflows dealing with many very large files where frequent changes are unlikely.

1.2.3 Code Changes

The key code changes involve:

- Adding the `--max-checksum-file-size` parameter to the Snakemake argument parser.
- Modifying the `check_files` function to respect the new parameter when determining whether to compute checksums for files.
- Updating the documentation to explain the new parameter and its implications.

1.2.4 Impact

This change provides users with greater control over the performance and accuracy of Snakemake's DAG building process. It allows them to optimize the workflow for their specific use case, balancing the need for accurate change detection with the desire for fast DAG generation.

1.2.5 Associated Project Workitem

- [Link to the issue](#)
- [Link to the pull request](#)

1.3 Acknowledgement

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